

IT'S PSYCHOLOGICAL

Mental Health & India

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ABOUT US

It is a great pleasure to present you all the fifth edition of IT'S PSYCHOLOGICAL, a quarterly magazine by the Chittmanthan All India Psychology Club. Nearly three years ago we the ex-students of Psychology department, University of Allahabad started this student initiated club with motto 'Connect, Communicate, Collaborate'. The mission is to operationalize our passion for the field of Psychology outside classroom with the visionary idea of building a facilitative learning environment so that knowledge obtained can be practiced for community welfare. A club that didn't exist few years ago, now is a family of nearly 650 global members and has successfully conducted a decent number of quizzes and webinars, plus numerous posts, photo galleries and updates on intriguing contemporary topics of Psychology. So, in a way, this success is the best possible case for IT'S PSYCHOLOGICAL magazine, which will appear online here quarterly. We designed this magazine with the purpose of spreading the outreach of Psychology. The agenda is to search the ways to make the best use of the knowledge of Psychology so that it can touch everyday life and promote wellness. This initiative also comes at an extraordinary time when there is a great need to connect the eminent educationists, scholars and curious learners of Psychology to communicate and collaborate for the global well-being. The wellness of mind and body is the priority but that doesn't mean to be influenced by the 'fake positivity'. This reminds me of the quote by Lori Deschene, " You don't have to be positive all the time. It's perfectly okay to feel sad, angry, annoyed, frustrated, scared and anxious. Having feelings doesn't make you a negative person. It makes you human." Welcome, let's take small steps towards wellness by diving into the understanding of Mental Health and India.

- Neerja Kushwaha
Head, Executive

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P R E F A C E

हो गई है पीर पर्वत-सी पिघलनी चाहिए,
इस हिमालय से कोई गंगा निकलनी चाहिए।
सिर्फ हंगामा खड़ा करना मेरा मकसद नहीं,
सारी कोशिश है कि ये सूरत बदलनी चाहिए।

-दुष्यन्त कुमार

If 'mental health crisis in India' was a student, its report card would boast of high percentage in varied subjects (here, symptoms amounting disorders and illness). Statistics and figures about the same paint a grim picture of reality that a large number of people are trying to escape, or are fighting with all their might. Many of us are taking precautionary measures towards what is being labeled as the next pandemic. At the same time, many of us find it a mere hoax.

The concept of mental health is often presented either in binarity with mental illness (es) or coupled with them. That mental health of one's own self and that of others is an independent entity is not often thought of. In a scenario like this, prioritizing one's mental health is often seen as a setback for a socially active human. A time for healing is looked down upon. The notion of 'no gains without pains', puts too much pressure on each generation, in most cohorts; only the degree of pressure may vary among them.

In a collectivist society like that of India, which has its foundations in the intimacy and harmony among familial and social connections, and the strength and security thus offered to its members, understanding, acceptance and awareness about mental health and different types of mental illness is crucial for the overall well-being of an individual, his family and friends, the society and for the generations to come.

As we usher into this New Year, amidst the cold wave, we can try to be the sunshine in our own lives and of those around us, when skies are grey. And this can be achieved with the first step of listening and accepting the feelings, and the world view of those who are suffering.

So, with this edition of our magazine, we make a humble attempt to understand mental health in India through experiences and expressions of people, and sensitize our readers about mental health of people around them through knowledge on the topic. Thus, in this edition, we let the stream of poetry and art poured out by our contributors flow in an untamed fashion. To show that there is light at the end of the abyss of mental illnesses, we have included the success story of the people who are getting better.

This edition comprises of three areas. The academic area includes biographies of two psychologists (one Indian and one western) crucial to the field of Positive Psychology, informative articles regarding the mental health concerns of people, especially of children and adolescents, and emerging mental health phenomena and issues. Applied area contains opinions and thoughts on psychological perspectives of how different dimensions of Positive Psychology like spiritual and emotional intelligence may combat and mitigate mental health woes. We have also included a research idea that holds the potential to provide psychological care for victims.

To arouse our interests in Psychology, mental health, and in our magazine, we have included a section containing psychology news and word search. This time, we have an exciting addition to the creative area, apart from poetries and drawings- memes! It is because nothing is as succinct, suitable and relatable form of an expression than a good meme.

As 2022 marked the 100th birth anniversary of Prof. Durganand Sinha, one of the most important figures in the history of Psychology, Club Chittmanthan played an imperative role in enacting a play and thus, celebrating his legacy along with many other functions, the report of which is also included for our readers.

We curate this edition in such a way that it not only stares at the impending doom of mental health crisis in India and novel mental health issues, but also providing evidence-backed manageable solutions, and psychology news, which spotlights the developmental measures taken by Indian Government in tackling the crisis. With this magazine, we intend to spread the outreach of psychology and its implications in improving mental health not just to Indians, but to every human life on the Earth.

Since academicians and scholars have differences regarding the various interventions discussed in this edition, we also have some limitations due to the discrepancy in the opinions of many stakeholders in this field. This magazine envisions building a more harmonious world and its unit, the human, in such times that we are experiencing. It is our hope that the scope of psychological inquiry in the pursuit of understanding mental health behaviours and actions would expand and help people become empathetic towards people with dissenting viewpoints. We hope this magazine will offer you opportunities to delve into various dimensions of mental health with a novel stance.

We offer our sincere gratitude to the contributors, students and eminent educationalists who have worked industriously towards bettering this magazine and who trusted us and shared their creative work for their edition. We would be delighted to publish any articles/ stories/ drawings/ poetries that you wish to submit, and together, we will increment the spectrum of our knowledge of this discipline and our valuable insight into the field.

Best wishes and thank you in advance for your contributions to 'It's Psychological: Small Steps Towards Well-Being.'

Shriya Mishra
Editor-in-Chief
(Fifth Edition)

Biography of Abraham Maslow

Gobind

Assistant Professor, Department of Applied Psychology
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“One of the goals of education should be to teach that life is precious”

The humanistic approach is regarded as having been founded by Abraham Maslow, its spiritual founder. Maslow was born in Brooklyn, New York, in 1908. His parents were immigrants with no formal schooling, and limited opportunities to improve their meager financial situation. Maslow’s father had such a strong desire to travel to America

that at the age of fourteen, he hitchhiked and travelled from Russia across Western Europe. His mother was a monstrous being (quoted in Hoffman, 1996, p.2). He grew up lonely and sad without loving parents or close friends. His father was distant and frequently left his troubled marriage. According to Maslow, his father “liked whiskey, women, and fights” (quoted in Wilson, 1972, p. 131). Maslow’s bond with

his mother deteriorated over time. Maslow never forgot how she treated him, and he declined to go to her funeral after she passed away. His psychological works as well as his emotional life have both been influenced by the tragedy.

Maslow once thought he was unique among children. Maslow admitted to the interviewer, “I was all alone in the world.” Maslow resorted to books after his initial attempts at retribution to get noticed and accepted as an athlete failed. Reading and education marked the route out of the Ghetto of starvation and loneliness, and the library became the playground in his infancy and adolescence. Early memories of Maslow are important because they reveal the type of life-

the life of scholarship- that he would create for himself. Maslow and his wife were married when he was twenty and she was nineteen years old. Maslow received a sense of direction and belonging from the union. After receiving his PhD from the University of Wisconsin in 1934, Maslow moved to New York for a postdoctoral appointment at

Columbia University. He later taught at Brooklyn College, where he remained wed until 1951.

In New York in 1940, Maslow met with Karen Horney and Alfred Adler. Additionally, he meets Ruth Benedict, an American anthropologist, and Max Werthiemer, a Gestalt psychologist. He developed the idea of self-actualization as a result of his adoration for Benedict and the Werthiemer.

He would strive to enhance human nature and show that individuals are capable of acting in ways other than prejudice, hatred, and aggressiveness. Maslow lectured at Massachusetts' Brandies University from 1951 until 1969. His migration to California to work on his humanistic psychology-based philosophy of politics, economics, and ethics was made possible by a foundation grant. In psychology and with the general public, he rose to enormous popularity. He was elected president of the American Psychological Association in 1967 and garnered numerous accolades. Maslow passed away in 1970 from a severe heart attack that he had while walking around his swimming pool, an activity that his physician had advised.